

OVERVIEW STUDY OF CURRENTLY USED INNOVATIVE TEACHING METHODS AT SLOVAK TECHNICAL UNIVERSITIES

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Abstract

Our contribution provides an overview of innovative teaching methods and forms that are used today at Slovak universities, primarily those that are technically oriented. We focus mainly on methods and forms of teaching in areas such as mathematics, statistics, and related data analysis, respectively on technical subjects. Our claims are supported by the results of a survey obtained through a questionnaire addressed to randomly selected teachers at Slovak universities with the above specialisation.

Keywords

Education at technical universities, Innovative teaching methods, Questionnaire, Overview study

1 Introduction

The quality of Slovak education is declining in international comparisons. This is evidenced, for example, by the deteriorating indicators in the PISA and PIAAC tests. In the ranking of world universities in 2023, Slovak University ranked 589th as the best. A significant part of high school graduates continues their university studies abroad, especially to the neighboring Czech Republic. According to the Czech Ministry of Education, 20 900 Slovak students studied at Czech universities last year. Most have no plans to return to Slovakia after completing their studies. Slovakia is, therefore, forced to look for ways to motivate young people not to leave.

2 Overview of the current state of the issue

Lectures are a well-known form of teaching in tertiary education. However, as described by (Sivarajah et al., 2019) there are many newer innovative teaching skills, pedagogical techniques and forms of educational technology that teachers can use. The role of universities as a source of knowledge for regional innovation processes was investigated by (Fritsch & Slavtchev, 2007). Many innovative teaching methods in higher education are constantly being developed to engage students better and improve their learning. Some innovative methods will be mentioned further in the article.

Problem-based learning and Project-based learning are student-centred learning approaches that involve active learning, critical thinking, and application of knowledge in

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practical scenarios. While problem-based learning aims to facilitate student learning by solving complex real-world problems, project-based learning involves the creation of some output, namely a project. (Maros, 2023), (Tsybulsky, 2019)

The Flipped Classroom involves an inversion of the traditional teaching methods. (Sertic at al., 2020) This method involves students engaging with lecture material at home through videos or readings, while class time is devoted to discussions, problem-solving, and interactive activities.

Active learning can be ensured by encouraging students to be actively involved in the learning process through discussions, debates, case studies and practical activities instead of passively listening to lectures.

The Jigsaw method is a pedagogical strategy that promotes collaboration and mutual learning among students. It is based on the principle that a group of students is divided into smaller "expert" groups, where each member studies a specific aspect of the material and then shares this information with others in the main group. The meta-analysis (Solissa at al, 2023) concluded that the jigsaw model of learning based on higher-order thinking skills has a significant impact on the thinking of 21st century students. This cooperative method can support inclusive education for all only through thoughtful preparation of teachers (Drouet et al., 2020), (Cochon Drouet at al., 2023)

Inquiry-based learning fosters critical thinking, problem-solving, research, and communication skills. It promotes a deeper understanding of concepts and encourages lifelong learning by nurturing curiosity and independent thinking in students. Because it relates to inquiry and research, it has its place in technical universities. (Jungman, 2019), (Kori, 2021)

The "use the design thinking process" method is a creative and systematic approach to problem-solving and innovation, often used in developing new products, services, or processes. Although it is used in many areas, it also has its benefits in technical education, from business and innovation to creating user-friendly products or services. The influence of problem-solving ability and creativity of students has been proven (Guaman-Quintanilla et al., 2023).

3D printing applications in education support interactive and experiential learning that helps students better understand the subject matter and develop practical skills that are important for their future. Teaching sustainability using 3D printing in engineering education was presented in an observational study (To et al., 2023)

The ideal solution is personalised learning, where creating individual student learning plans, adaptive software, and mentoring can help students access relevant information while supporting their strengths. Here, we see the possibilities soon of the involvement of artificial intelligence in education (Gillani et al., 2023), (Chiu et al., 2023).

Today, information and communication technologies (ICT) are among the innovations that have revolutionised various areas of the world, including education.

ICT is important in education because such platforms and opportunities have recently been created that have facilitated knowledge acquisition and significantly enabled the improvement of learning in an online environment (Hrablik Chovanová, 2023). Students have an increased awareness regarding the usefulness and advantages of e-learning (Al-Fraihat et al., 2020). The study's conclusion (Alhefnawi, 2021) claims that the Internet as a class presentation method is less effective than teaching through direct, active, face-to-face lectures. However, the observed difference between the two was small and limited.

Many authors of articles dealt with online education in connection with the Covid-19 pandemic. Education was one of the main areas disrupted by this pandemic. The pandemic has been a catalyst for online advancements in educational practices, and it has accelerated the use of the latest ICT. According to UNESCO statistics, the closure of universities worldwide to limit the Covid-19 pandemic has affected 91% of the student population. The coronavirus

outbreak forced the university to launch e-learning programs to ensure regular teaching (Mushtaha et al., 2022). Faculty members and students had to use high-tech tools and platforms to guarantee continuous teaching and learning (Sofi-Karim et al., 2023). Individual universities were forced to create new study plans that made it possible to acquire new competencies and consider new teaching methods., which resulted in several challenges (Ingaldi et al., 2023). Many studies have analysed the effects of online learning on teaching during the Covid-19 pandemic, for example, in Italy (Mari et al., 2021), in India (Mishra et al., 2020), in Brunei (Haidi & Hamdan, 2023), in South Korea (Ke & Zhang, 2023), in the United Kingdom universities (Al-Fraihat et al., 2020). Student evaluation of online learning during the COVID-19 pandemic was investigated in Poland (Szopiński & Bachnik, 2022) and other countries.

Cloud computing teaching (learning in the cloud) involves using cloud technologies and platforms to provide educational content and teaching materials to students and teachers. This form of education takes advantage of cloud services, such as access to information and applications via the Internet. (Sabadash, 2023) Online teaching methods based on Artificial Intelligence and edge calculation using edge-cloud computing platforms are described in (Zhong, 2023).

Integrating technologies using digital tools, educational applications, virtual reality, and interactive platforms provides space for creating engaging and dynamic learning experiences. It can be concluded that digital technologies show a range of tools, including formalised learning environments in higher education teaching, and students use these tools to support their learning (Alenezi, 2023). Globally, engineering education is experiencing a shift from teacher-centred to student-centred teaching and learning, from content-based learning to outcome-based learning, from knowledge-providing teachers to teacher-facilitators, from lecture-based learning to learning technology-based (Milićević, 2021).

Blended learning is an educational approach combining traditional face-to-face instruction with online learning activities or resources. It is a flexible model that integrates the best aspects of both offline and online learning environments to create a comprehensive and effective learning experience and adapt to different learning styles and student preferences. (Okaz, 2015), (Leininger-Frézal, 2023) After the end of the COVID-19 pandemic, blended learning has become extremely widespread, especially in higher education. (Yang, 2023),

3 Implementation of the survey and obtained results

Our survey focused on using innovative teaching methods at technical universities. It was implemented in the form of a short online questionnaire. 150 randomly selected teachers at Slovak universities were approached and asked to answer questions. Teachers who teach mathematics or technical subjects were preferred. Considering the area of our research, we were interested in what methods and forms of teaching our colleagues prefer in their classes today and whether they have retained some elements of online teaching since the COVID-19 pandemic. Out of 150 distributed questionnaires, 22 were returned, i.e. approximately 14.67 percent.

To the question of which of the teaching methods and forms are used by university teachers in the teaching process, we obtained the following answers shown in Fig. 1. Almost all respondents (21 out of 22 respondents) stated that they use the interpretation of the curriculum in their pedagogical practice (21 answers out of 101 of all answers, i.e. 20.79%). This finding corresponds to the overall statistics of the Learning Makes Sense project regarding the teaching methods and forms used in our universities. (Mesa 10) Considering the difficulty of the curriculum, this fact is understandable. The effort of university teachers to develop

students' critical analytical thinking is reflected in the use of the method of solving problems with students (16 answers out of 101, i.e. 15.84%). Applying theoretical knowledge to practical examples is also an effort to connect university education with technical practice (14 answers out of 101, i.e. 13.86%). For students, consultations with their teacher are indispensable during their studies; therefore, teachers also often include them in their pedagogical activities (14 answers out of 101, i.e. 13.86%). Also, the ability to discuss and work in a team is important from the point of view of the future practice of engineers, and therefore, good teachers often include them in classes (13 answers out of 101, i.e. 12.87%). Nowadays, the relatively frequent use of e-learning is also related to the development of ICT (9 answers out of 101, i.e. 8.91%). We assume that the development of e-learning is related to the fact that many e-materials had to be prepared during the previous years of the COVID-19 pandemic. Individual self-study is typical for the education of university students. (3 answers out of 101, i.e. 2.97%). It is used primarily in their home preparation and not in the classroom. It is excellent if the teacher knows how to motivate students to self-study already during the semester, not only during their exam period. To be effective, self-study must be correctly managed. The answers to the questionnaire also mention the option of teaching one subject by multiple subject matter experts (3 answers out of 101, i.e. 2.97%). It would be excellent if the school could provide and ensure this opportunity for its students, especially if they are experts in the practice field. We also recorded two responses where interactive learning was mentioned. (2 answers out of 101, i.e. 1.98%). For example, we see a great benefit for technical fields when students can acquire the necessary skills and habits through the provided simulation applications. Creating such a simulation application is indeed difficult. However, we see its subsequent contribution as enormous. We did not have any answers regarding reading texts important for the studied area in our questionnaire. We see this as logical for technical universities. We can imagine it, for example, for the study of law and the interpretation of studied laws, which, however, was not our area of interest.

Fig. 1: Use of teaching methods and forms at Slovak universities according to our questionnaire

We are aware that the use of teaching methods and forms is conditioned by time availability and the type of school subject. The number of students a university teacher has in

his class is also an important factor. That's why, as we mentioned above, we focused our research on the areas of mathematics and statistics close to us. Subsequently, we looked for connections between the size of study groups and preferred teaching methods and forms.

We expected that there would be a relationship between study group size and preferred study methods and forms. However, no connection has been proven. The most frequently mentioned group sizes at universities by teachers were 10-20 students and 20-30 students. But neither here nor with groups of more than 40 students or less than 5 students, certain same or similar teaching methods and forms were not preferred. The implemented teaching method is probably most influenced by the teacher's personality. Respectively, according to the given studied sample, it is impossible to predict the dependence of the method and form of teaching on the student sample size. Innovative methods are also used by teachers with large numbers of students, where we expected their frequency to be lower. The results also do not indicate any relationship between class size and preferred innovative teaching methods.

Teachers were asked to describe what is typical of their teaching briefly. Thanks to their open approach, we got these answers. The responses are presented in random order, although some statements were repetitive; for example, discussion with students was a frequent element. Due to the researched area, solving the tasks was also typical. Selected answers are:

- solving examples from practice,
- logical explanation of the principles of technical drawing based on production requirements,
- use of practical examples in teaching, comparison of theoretical approaches and their real use in practice,
- adapting to the student's pace, from simpler to more complex,
- leading students to independence in their work,
- variety of methods used,
- discussion with students,
- communication with students,
- student activity,
- projects,
- presentations,
- use of available software,
- explanation and motivation of students during lectures, discussion of problems when solving projects,
- brainstorming,
- solving examples from practice using free software,
- consistency,
- communication with students and establishing direct contact at the blackboard,
- emphasis on solving examples from practice and searching for the most common cases and situations where theoretical knowledge can be applied,
- solution of sample tasks.

The chart in Fig. 2 shows the proportion of respondents' answers to the question of their use of innovative teaching methods. The types of innovative methods offered in the questionnaire were selected from Innovative Teaching Methods with Guide and Examples (Best in 2023) according to (Tran, 2023).

The answers to the direct question about using innovative methods were split 19/3 in favour of innovative methods. Nineteen respondents to the questionnaire stated that they actively use innovative methods in their classes. On the contrary, three university teachers say they do not use innovative methods. Eighteen respondents indicated a total of 67 of the offered innovative teaching methods. We also recorded one answer, "others", where the respondent states that they use eduScrum and mini PBL methods.

According to the results of the questionnaire, Slovak university teachers prefer project teaching (11 answers out of 67, i.e. 16.42%) and teaching based on peer feedback (10 answers out of 67, i.e. 14.93%) as part of innovative teaching methods. The third largest share of responses was expressed in blended teaching (7 responses out of 67, i.e. 10.45%). Next in order are the use of virtual reality technology and crossover learning (5 answers out of 67, i.e. 7.46%) and the use of the design-thinking process and inquiry-based learning (4 responses out of 67, i.e. 5.97%). The use of AI in education, 3D printing, interactive lessons, cloud computing teaching, flipped classrooms and peer teaching were also indicated as innovative teaching methods (3 responses out of 67, i.e. 4.48%). In the questionnaire, we also registered the chosen jigsaw method and personalised teaching, but these answers were given with a low frequency (only 1 answer out of 67, i.e. 1.49%). As mentioned above, one answer, "others", contains an unmentioned eduScrum and mini PBL methods. Scrum is a well-developed method used mainly in the Netherlands and Germany, allowing people to work intensively in a team. Scrum was developed in the IT world for complex IT projects, while eduScrum focuses on learning (<https://eduscrum.org/>). Mini PBL is essentially project-based learning, while this method specialises in learning through short-term projects that we could apply, for example, in mathematics or statistics.

Fig. 2: Use of innovative teaching methods at Slovak universities according to our questionnaire

We also used questionnaires to determine if teachers retained any elements of online teaching from the Covid era. The surprising result was that 6 respondents out of a total of 22 respondents, i.e. 27.27%, said none. Most of the teachers said they kept all the prepared electronic materials for the students or used online consultations (occasionally, but some also regularly). Some teachers give students recorded exercises or videos of online lectures. Subsequently, they can devote more time to consultations, solving problems or other activities. Somewhere, large lectures run online for capacity reasons. The 3D interactive textbook also remained part of the education. Some teachers leave more assignments for homework. Some universities continue to use tried and tested specialised software for teaching. Student voting is also an element that has been successfully retained.

In our personal experience, students evaluated the provision of electronic materials very positively. One of the first questions students still have during face-to-face teaching at the first lecture is whether an electronic version of the presented materials will be provided. It is beneficial to have an electronic version of the presented materials available in sufficient time. Also, trial electronic tests, by which they receive immediate feedback, are positively appreciated by students.

4 Conclusion

If we want the school to effectively prepare young people for their future profession, it must adapt to the rapid changes in today's society. The need to find new, more effective education methods is related to this.

Our paper describes innovative methods of education that are commonly used today, especially at technical universities. Our survey also focused on those elements of education that remained part of tertiary education at universities even after the Covid period, in subjects such as mathematics, statistics and data analysis or in technical subjects.

While bringing innovative teaching strategies into the classroom used to be a narrow academic practice carried out by a few brave educators, our research shows that these strategies are commonplace today.

No, we do not want to say that a teacher who does not use innovative methods is bad or that his teaching is ineffective. In our opinion, it is always important that the teaching process focuses on the student's personality and adapts to his needs. But it is good to use all the opportunities the moment allows.

The testing results and current personal experiences from teaching at our universities indicate an inevitable change in the use of teaching methods and forms. At least we all know that the COVID-19 pandemic has accelerated changes in the use of information and communication technologies in the teaching process. Practice has shown that maintaining online education elements in face-to-face education brings many positives. It would be a big mistake not to take advantage of all the challenges we were forced to overcome during the pandemic because both students and teachers found their positives in the new methods, which they do not want to lose.

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